

An Internet Platform for Dissemination of Post Earthquake Safety Information, Enhancing Search and Rescue Operations

Ata Yalçın¹

Advisor: Prof. Dr. Ceylan Yozgatlıgil

Department of Computer Engineering, Middle East Technical University, Ankara, Türkiye

Abstract

An internet platform for the dissemination of safety information after an earthquake is presented. This platform enables the earthquake survivors to mark themselves as “safe”, this safety data is then shared among a list of people that were predetermined by the survivor. This one-to-many structure of information dissemination, coupled with the high bandwidth capacity of the current 4.5G internet technology has the potential to mitigate cellular congestion problems on the cellular networks which are using 2G or 3G technologies. Furthermore, earthquake survivors can mark their buildings’ statuses and mark whether they are in their buildings. A web API was developed to serve as a back end for a mobile client application that sends to the web platform the data of whether the client is at their building. Even though the development of such a mobile application is left outside of the scope of this project, the proposed model of pre-earthquake data collection is expected to increase the collection rate and accuracy of the data. The collected data related to the building’s status, people’s safety and whereabouts is then presented to the search and rescue operators. This data transmission is expected to enhance search and rescue operations primarily by enhancing the priority determination of operation locations.

Keywords: earthquake, search and rescue, congestion, internet platform
August, 2023

1. Introduction

Türkiye is one of the countries where earthquakes are frequently seen, and many active fault lines extend west-east direction along the country. The studies showed that cities such as Istanbul, Izmir, Malatya, Erzurum, Antakya and Van had faced many destructive earthquakes. According to earthquake catalogues, 12 earthquakes have caused significant damage in Istanbul in the last 1500 years. The Marmara Earthquake occurred on August 17, 1999, causing 17,479 deaths and 43,953 injuries. In the 1900s, 17 of the 124 earthquakes that caused more than 1000 deaths were on the territory of Turkey. According to calculations made in 2000, the probability of a strong earthquake

that will be effective in an area close to Istanbul in the next 30 years was found to be $62\pm 15\%$. [1]. Our high seismicity makes it essential to develop solutions to reduce earthquake mortality. After the collapse of buildings because of events such as earthquakes, terrorist attacks, and landslides, the accuracy of the search and rescue efforts is vital to find people trapped under the collapsed structures. The rapid commencement of search and rescue operations in the early hours of the disaster increases the survival rate. After 24 hours, the survival rate of disaster victims decreases by 50%. It is specified that 50–95% of those who were trapped under debris and survived after an earthquake are saved within the first 24–48 hours of the earthquake [2].

¹Ata Yalçın, ata.yalcin@metu.edu.tr

Figure 1. The graph of survival rate with respect to time.

As seen in [3, Figure 1: The graph of survival rate with respect to time.], people's rate of survival is dramatically increased when they are saved quickly. Data and predictions about the earthquake victims are necessary for search and rescue activities. Thus, it is of utmost importance to develop methods of acquiring this information as quickly as possible. [4] After the earthquake, people communicate by phone calls with their acquaintances in the earthquake area. The cellular call intensity experienced during a disaster event exceeds the infrastructure capacities of cellular communication services. This congestion causes interruptions in communication [5]. As an example after the earthquake in İzmir, people used their phones to get information from their close ones. Congestion problems occurred in cellular communications. Turkcell, Vodafone, and Türk Telekom were some of the firms that had this issue. [6] Similarly because of the earthquake in Istanbul on the 26'th of September at 13:59, Türk Telekom, Turkcell, and Vodafone had cellular communication problems. [7]

As presented in [8, Figure 2 : AFAD's notice on post-earthquake communications.], The Disaster and Emergency Management Presidency (AFAD), emphasize that in severe disaster or emergencies, instead of cellular call communications, internet-based services or short messaging service (SMS) should be used to maintain uninterrupted communication.

Facebook developed a technology for post-earthquake safety information sharing called the "Safety Check" EDR (Explicit Disaster Response) service. However, many Facebook users abstained from using this technology. One probable reason for this is the presence of a large group in people's social media networks. People were worried about sharing their safety data and locations with this large group. This phenomenon demon-

Figure 2. AFAD's notice on post-earthquake communications.

strates that sharing data only between close ones will reduce hesitation. Safety Check allowed users to mark themselves as safe but did not provide the option to mark themselves in danger. This phenomenon is unfit for the dangerous situations that might occur after the initial moments of an earthquake. [9]

A more advanced EDR system should have the following properties:

- People should be able to determine the members of the group with whom their safety statuses will be shared.
- People should be able to mark themselves as unsafe.
- People should be able to change their statuses over time.

Another criticism existing EDR systems face is that their activation depends entirely on a corporation. Thus, in some necessary situations, it might not be activated. Only instances of Facebook Safety Check activations in Turkey are: March 2016 Ankara bombed terror attack, February 2016 Istanbul bombed terror attack, June 2016 Istanbul bombed terror attack [10-12]. Similarly, an EDR service developed by Google: Google Person Finder is activated in Turkey only once in the October 2011 Van Earthquake [13]. The data collected by the EDR services can be shared with the S&R personnel and help enhance Search and rescue activities, but no such schema is present in present EDR services.

Thus, an advanced EDR system should have the following properties:

- Local officials should be able to activate the system.
- Collected data should be shared with R&D personnel.

2. Methodology

ASP.NET CORE framework was used in the development of this project. This framework's rich array of tools spanning a wide range of usages was worthy in this project particularly because of the fragmented nature of the project. These tools enabled a faster deployment of the authentication and authorization functionalities. The entity framework accelerated the development by a considerable margin since the provided abstractions over the database tables made the development process much simpler. One notable technology that proved helpful was the RAZOR pages. CRUD (create, read, update, delete) pages for modifications of entities were automatically created and necessary modifications to these pages were then applied. This workflow contributed considerably to the pace at which this project was developed.

3. Results and Discussion

Users' registrations can be done either by each user themselves using "register page" shown in Figure 3 Register Page or by an authorized person. Registration can be completed quickly by selecting options from combo boxes. In this process the data integrity is protected. For instance, when a city is selected, in the next dropdown input, the districts belong this city will be displayed and so on.

Figure 4: login page presents the login page which after successful authentication directs the user to the "status modification page" where the user's private information is displayed. On this page, all data belonging to the logged-in user is displayed such as status, password, address, and the list of people authorized to see the status of the user. The list of these people is determined by the user. Moreover, when a user enters the system, the user would see the persons who had permitted the user

to see his/her statuses on their private status modification page as seen in Figure 5:status modification page.

In the event of a disaster, let be an earthquake, when an apartment status, in any way, is declared as wholly or partially broken down, the system will designate the status of all people living in this apartment as Unknown. The authorized people can easily send video-audio-SMS or video-email to the residents of these apartments. On the SMS and Email page, there is one visible button with the caption 'I am safe.' Clicking on this button invokes a response that stores the user's safety status in the database. Using these SMSs and emails sent to their phones or email accounts, survivors will log in to the system and mark their statuses. If emails or SMSs are sent to the ones with the status of Unknown and answers are not received in a short time, it will be guessed that person is in danger. By evaluating other family members' answers, S&R teams can easily reach accurate opinions about victims.

Users can log in to the system at any time and declare their statuses directly. Since each user can determine who can view their status, relatives and friends who are curious about the user in the disaster region will be able to see their status on their own-user pages. This will reduce the cellular call volume which is an integral part of post-earthquake communication interruption mitigation.

Using "disaster regions page" shown in Figure 6 : disaster regions page, S&R teams can view the number and condition of everyone in the disaster area. It is reasonable that knowing the victims' age, gender, and apartment flat will help S&R teams make more accurate decisions in planning their operations. From this page, teams can observe the general situation of the people and apartments in this region. Using direction button, they can search in city, in district or in village levels.

Figure 3. Register Page

Figure 4: login page

Using direction buttons, authorized users can access the "Authorized status update page" as shown in Figure 7: Authorized status update page where each person's or apartment's status can be altered. This page can be used to send SMSs and Emails to each person. If a person is rescued safely from debris, S&R team members will change the victim's status to safe. If the victim is sent to a hospital, the team member will modify the victim's status as hospitalized, giving the hospital name.

After SMS and Emails are sent, authorized users can view the "SMS and email results page" as shown in Figure 8: SMS and email results page and see whether the message is transmitted and/or answered. This will enable them to plan their next action.

After an earthquake is over, overall data and statistics can be gathered from the "overall result query page" as shown in Figure 9: overall result query page by authorized personnel. This page enables the advanced editing and execution of SQL commands.

Authorizations are grouped under four categories: Administrator, Manager, Operator, and Search and Rescue Teams: These authorities may be at country, province, district, and village levels. A user of higher authority can assign lower-level authorizations using the "Authorization page" as shown in Figure 10: Authorization page.

A mobile application that updates the at-home status of the user by the user's location data might provide a faster data collection scheme. However, the development of such an application is kept outside of this project's scope. A web API is developed to handle the backend of such a mobile application. A JSON object containing username, password, and at-home status is transmitted to the API. The API authenticates the user by the provided username and password. If the authentication is successful, then at-home status of the

Figure 5. Status modification page

user is updated. This procedure is depicted in Figure 11: User Location Update -via Postman App.

4. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the development of a web platform that can facilitate post-earthquake data transfer and considerably enhance search and rescue operations. The main differences of this platform from other safety data management tools primarily embedded into social media platforms is its greater integration with the search and rescue operations, its focus on emergency response, richer attribute space for data collection and faster data collection due to pre-earthquake data collection scheme. However even with this advanced features, more technical knowledge should be applied to this concept to increase its applicability. The development of the mobile application with the provided API connection procedure would provide a significant leap forward for this concept. Another critical aspect of a project of this scale would be security. The proposed model forces the mobile application to in-device storage of the user's password, a significant vulnerability for the system's overall safety. Implementing authentication technologies such as JWT (JSON Web Tokens) would remove this necessity and thus drastically increase the system's overall safety. Another critical point is the operability of the project. The server should be able to handle the increased traffic after an earthquake; noting that this large-scale traffic occurs quite rarely, a cloud solution seems applicable.

5. Acknowledgments

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to Professor Ceylan Yozatligil for her invaluable support to this project.

This research received funding from Adımodtü Undergraduate Research Programme.

Figure 6. Disaster regions page

Figure 7. Authorized status update page

Figure 8. SMS and email results page

Figure 9. Overall result query page

6. References

- [1] A. Gündüz, S. Türkmen, U. Eryigit, Y. Karaca, and M. Aydın, 'Is Turkey an Earthquake Country?/Türkiye Bir Deprem Ülkesi midir?', Eurasian Journal of Emergency Medicine, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 33, 2013.
- [2] G. Yılmaz and S. Demiröz Yıldırım, 'Afetlerde kentsel arama ve kurtarmada kullanılan yöntemler ve güncel yaklaşımların değerlendirilmesi', 2020.
- [3] A. W. Coburn, R. J. S. Spence, and A. Pomonis, 'Factors determining human casualty levels in earthquakes: mortality prediction in building collapse', in Proceedings of the Tenth World Conference on earthquake engineering, 1992, vol. 10, pp. 5989–5994.
- [4] T. Feng et al., 'Estimation of earthquake casualties using high-resolution remote sensing: a case study of Dujiangyan city in the May 2008 Wenchuan earthquake', Natural hazards, vol. 69, no. 3, pp. 1577–1595, 2013.
- [5] D. Satoh, Y. Takano, R. Sudo, and T. Mochida, 'Reduction of communication demand under disaster congestion using control to change human communication behaviour without direct restriction', Computer Networks, vol. 134, pp. 105–115, 2018.
- [6] "Telefonlar neden çekmiyor?" Cnnturk, 2020. <https://www.cnnturk.com/teknoloji/telefonlar-neden-cekmiyor-deprem-sonrasi-turkcell-vodafone-ve-turk-telekom-coktu-mu> (accessed 7.12.2020).
- [7] "Depremde Tüm Gsm Operatörleri Çöktü", Branding Türkiye, Sep. 27, 2019. <https://www.brandingturkiye.com/depreme-tum-gsm-operatorleri-coktu/> (accessed Jan. 06, 2023).
- [8] "AFAD, İzmir'deki Deprem Sonrası Uyardı: SMS'i Tercih Edin", NTV, 30-Oct-2020. <https://www.ntv.com.tr/turkiye/afad-izmirdeki-deprem-sonrasi-uyardi-sms-i-tercih-edin,f-4D3zPLmH0OQSICQWPfFjw>. (Accessed: 06-Jan-2023).
- [9] K. S. Lee, 'Explicit disaster response features in social media: safety check and community help usage on Facebook during Typhoon Mangkhut', in Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Human-Computer Interaction with Mobile Devices and Services, 2019, pp. 1–12.
- [10] "Facebook let you change your profile picture for Paris, but it won't for Ankara," The Independent, Mar. 14, 2016. <https://www.independent.co.uk/tech/ankara-bombing-facebook-turns-on-safety-check-feature-as-it-did-for-paris-shootings-but-will-not-add-option-to-change-profile-picture-a6930761.html> (accessed Jan. 06, 2023).
- [11] "Facebook Safety Check Uygulamasını Ankara'daki Patlamanın Ardından Devreye Soktu" Teknoloji Paylaşım Portalı, 2016. <https://webinyo.com/facebook-safety-check-uygulamasini-ankaradaki-patlamanin-ardindan-devreye-soktu.html> (accessed 07.12.2020).
- [12] J. Rogers, "Facebook activates Safety Check after Istanbul airport attack" Fox News, Jun. 28, 2016. <https://www.foxnews.com/tech/facebook-activates-safety-check-after-istanbul-airport-attack> (accessed Jan. 06, 2023).
- [13] D. McCarra, "Google launches Person Finder in Turkey following 7.2 magnitude earthquake," The Sociable, Oct. 24, 2011. <https://sociable.co/technology/google-launches-person-finder-in-turkey-following-7-2-magnitude-earthquake/> (accessed Jan. 06, 2023).

Figure 10. Authorization page

Figure 11. User Location Update - via Postman App